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Deliverable 4.3

Software repository of ML and DA algorithms of T4.2.1-T4.4.3

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Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	D4.3
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2026-06-30	Version	2

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Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	D4.3
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2026-06-30	Version	2

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Executive Summary	4
2. Scope	4
3. Description of the ML and DA code repositories	4
3.1 MuSt3Net in the Mediterranean Sea (task T4.2.1).....	4
3.2 EmuPML in the North West Shelf (task T4.2.1).....	5
3.3 Interpolation of benthic traits with DINCAE (task T4.2.2).....	5
3.4 Interpolation of pollutant (Hg) with SOM (task T4.2.2).....	5
3.5 Nitrate bias correction using ML algorithm in NWS (task T4.2.3).....	6
3.6 Spatial distribution of zooplankton (task T4.3.1)	6
3.7 Diel vertical migration of mesozooplankton (task T4.3.2).....	7
3.8 Fish migration (task T4.3.3).....	7
3.9 Super Resolution Data Assimilation (task T4.4.3).....	8
3.10 Assimilation of new type of observations in MED (task T4.4.2)	8
3.11 Assimilation of new type of observations in NWS (task T4.4.2).....	9
3.12 Assimilation of new type of observations in BLK (task T4.4.2).....	9
4. Conclusions.....	9
Reference	10

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	D4.3
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2026-06-30	Version	2

1. Executive Summary

A central objective of NECCTON is the construction of new codes and algorithms to push forward the state-of-the-art of the Copernicus Marine Service in integrating numerical model simulations and new and consolidated types of observations. A list of algorithms based on machine learning and data assimilation have been developed in the tasks T4.2, T4.3 and T4.4 of the work package 4. The algorithms are shared internally and externally to the project through GitHub repositories following the guidelines described in deliverable 4.1 (Brajard et al., 2023). The codes are shared through a NECCTON common organization <https://github.com/neccton-algo>. The list of new algorithms includes emulators of ocean models, methods for the interpolation of satellite and sparse in situ data, methods for bias correction of model results, methods to handle zooplankton and fish data, and approaches for the assimilation of new type of observations.

The codes are described in the GitHub repositories and recalled in section 3 of this document. For each algorithm, the text includes code repository link, code owner and a brief description of the code.

2. Scope

This document provides the access to the repositories of Data Assimilation (DA) and Machine Learning (ML) software developed in the task T4.2, T4.3 and T4.4. The deliverable is organized as a GitHub repository (<https://github.com/neccton-algo>) containing the codes for machine learning and data assimilation developed within the project NECCTON which follows the D4.1 guidelines.

3. Description of the ML and DA code repositories

The code repositories are summarized below.

3.1 MuSt3Net in the Mediterranean Sea (task T4.2.1)

Emulator for unobserved variables in the Mediterranean Sea. The Convolutional Neural Network allows to emulate the 3D results of a biogeochemical model also integrating observations from BGC-Argo data when variable is available (Task 4.2.1).

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/MuSt3Net>

Contacts: Teresa Tonelli (ttonelli@ogs.it)

Code description: A deep-learning approach to perform model-data fusion, focused on generating new 3D maps of chlorophyll-a by (a) modelling its relationship with physical variables, and (b) merging in-situ observations (i.e. BGC-Argo). This novel approach consisting of a two-phase training procedure, designed to integrate different data sources, preserving and spreading their information. In the first phase, the network learns to model spatial and temporal dependencies using numerical model data

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	D4.3
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2026-06-30	Version	2

alone, while the second phase then incorporates real float measurements, refining the predictions by adapting to in-situ observations and extending their information over the 3D domain.

3.2 EmuPML in the North West Shelf (task T4.2.1)

A neural network deriving from a set of observable variables (surface phytoplankton functional type chlorophyll-a, sea surface temperature, sea surface salinity), atmospheric variables (wind speed, short-wave radiation), river discharge data and structural data (coordinates, bathymetry, day of the year), variety of surface and vertically averaged carbon pools: detrital carbon, DOC, zooplankton carbon, heterotrophic bacteria carbon and DIC.

Code: https://github.com/neccton-algo/ML_carbon_pools/tree/main

Contacts: Jozef Skakala (jos@pml.ac.uk)

Code description: Python code based on Keras/Tensorflow library, delivering a feed-forward Neural Network model (in fact a deep ensemble of 15 such models was used) trained on a 5 year ERSEM model free simulation and validated using Copernicus reanalysis for the same period, i.e. the NWSHELF_MULTIYEAR_PHY_004_009 product.

3.3 Interpolation of benthic traits with DINCAE (task T4.2.2)

Neural Network interpolation of sparse observation of benthic habitats using model outputs

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/DINCAE-benthic-traits>

Contacts: Abel Dechenne (adechenne@uliege.be) and Alexander Barth (a.barth@uliege.be)

Code description: Julia code based on Flux.jl library. It interpolates points with a convolutional neural network. The training is based on 211 stations in the Black Sea continental shelf. Each station is associated to 27 different biological traits. Each trait has different modalities (3 to 6) that represent the different expression of the traits. These modalities are trained together within the model. To extend the training dataset, model outputs from the Black Sea (<https://doi.org/10.48670/mds-00354>) are used: average oxygen concentration, bottom flux, average Particulate Organic Carbon concentration and sedimentary flux. Along that, bathymetry and sediment types also feed the model. The output is: a map of the interpolated traits along the continental slope and an estimated error by the model based on the training data.

3.4 Interpolation of pollutant (Hg) with SOM (task T4.2.2)

Interpolator for non-observed variables using Self-Organizing Map (SOM) analysis on a dataset of mercury-related oceanographic observations.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	D4.3
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2026-06-30	Version	2

Code: https://github.com/neccton-algo/Hg_SOM

Contacts: Marco Puglia (mpuglia@ogs.it)

Code description: The code starts by loading the required packages (for *Octave-10.3.0*), then reads the CSV dataset, and extracts the four relevant columns containing mercury, temperature, salinity, and oxygen concentrations. These variables are wrapped into a self-organizing-map (SOM) data structure with assigned names. The entire dataset is normalized by variable so that each component has comparable scale before training. The script defines the SOM training configuration, then it trains the SOM using the `som_make` function. After the SOM is trained, it identifies which map unit best matches each data sample, and calculates the key SOM quality metrics, the distance matrix (U-Matrix), its components for each variable, and assess how well the map represents the dataset. In the end, all relevant variables produced during the workflow are saved into a designated `.mat` file. After this step, plots are made. Next, the mercury dataset is projected onto the trained model output. The model output is normalized using the same scaling parameters applied to the previously normalized observational data. The determination of the Best Matching Units (BMUs) is then repeated on this augmented dataset. Following BMU assignment, the results are de-normalized by applying the inverse transformation derived from the normalized mercury observations. Finally, the spatial distribution of the projected mercury concentrations on the model is visualized across multiple depth layers.

3.5 Nitrate bias correction using ML algorithm in NWS (task T4.2.3)

Machine-learning reconstruction of surface nitrate for the North-West European Shelf, built directly from observations, riverine discharge, atmospheric, and Copernicus reanalysis inputs.

Code: https://github.com/neccton-algo/NO3_Emulator_NECCTON

Contacts: Deep Banerjee (dba@pml.ac.uk) and Jozef Skakala (jos@pml.ac.uk)

Code description: The codebase follows a modular workflow. It pulls together all required predictors sea surface temperature (SST), chlorophyll groups, net primary production (NPP), river loads, ERA5 fields, bathymetry and time-of-year variables, aligns them on a common grid, and collocates them with nitrate measurements in the database of ICES. The neural network is built and tuned using AutoKeras, which handles the architecture search and training. Once the best model is selected, the script evaluates its performance on the independent test datasets and then runs it across the full 1998–2020 period to generate the gap-free nitrate fields.

3.6 Spatial distribution of zooplankton (task T4.3.1)

Machine learning for spatial distribution analysis of zooplankton diversity linking zooplankton taxonomic and functional diversity datasets (e.g. metabarcoding, metagenomics and imaging data from Zooscan and UVP) to physics and LTL outputs of the Copernicus Marine Service GLO model.

Code: https://github.com/neccton-algo/PNMI_ML/tree/v1.0

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	D4.3
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2026-06-30	Version	2

Contacts: Laetitia Drago (laetitia.drago@locean.ipsl.fr) and Sakina-Dorothee Ayata (sakina-dorothee.ayata@locean.ipsl.fr)

Code description: R pipeline computing diversity metrics for plankton communities and exploring their relationships with the Copernicus Marine Service oceanographic variables. Initial regression models for diversity, biomass, and abundance showed poor performance, so we adopted binary classification (High/Low, threshold at median) using XGBoost and Boosted Regression Trees.

3.7 Diel vertical migration of mesozooplankton (task T4.3.2)

A Decision Tree approach to relate the underwater photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) located at the upper and lower boundaries of the high concentration layer of mesozooplankton (and small fish) to surface environmental condition (i.e. instantaneous surface PAR, daily averaged surface PAR, day-length, integrated food for mesozooplankton). The related environmental conditions and underwater PAR are subsequently coded in respective biogeochemical models for use during simulations.

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/DVM>

Contacts: Veli Çağlar Yumruktepe, caglar.yumruktepe@nersc.no

Code description: The branch has a Jupyter notebook and various input files. The notebook first reads acoustics data (an example for a mooring site is included in the notebook), post-processes (taking anomalies at depth, takes weekly averages, normalizes to the maximum value for each profile). A similar approach is applied to an example 1D-run for this location to extract underwater PAR. The notebook also includes scripts to obtain and ice-cover correct surface PAR. These are run for the example mooring site in the notebook, but the codes are written in a generic manner to replicate for any other region. Before decision tree algorithms, the notebook prepares a dictionary file that has the inputs (i.e. instantaneous surface PAR, daily averaged surface PAR, day-length, integrated food for mesozooplankton) and underwater PAR located at the upper and lower band of the high concentration layer. The dictionary content is then divided into four subsets (i.e. polar night, polar day, day/night cycle). The estimated PAR against input data in the form of decision trees is the output of this notebook. The tree is then expected to be codes with if/else cases in Fortran for the respective biogeochemical models.

3.8 Fish migration (task T4.3.3)

A machine learning framework for simultaneous data assimilation and model tuning has been implemented in PyTorch.

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/coda>

Contacts: David Greenberg (david.greenberg@hereon.de)

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	D4.3
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2026-06-30	Version	2

Code description: this software package implements CODA (Combined Optimization of Dynamics and Assimilation), an algorithm for tuning simulation parameters and sub-grid-scale parametrizations directly on observation data. During training, a neural network processes a space-time patch of partial observations, and generates an assimilated system state as output. This output is used as the initial conditions for a simulation, which is then compared to observations using one or more observation operators. By processing two overlapping windows of observations, CODA also computes an additional model consistency loss term based on weak-constraint 4DVar. Unlike DA methods based on supervised machine learning, CODA never requires access to ground truth system states. Within the NECCTON project, CODA is being used to develop and test parametrizations of horizontal fish migration.

3.9 Super Resolution Data Assimilation (task T4.4.3)

A Neural Network allowing to go from a low resolution (LR) field to a high resolution (HR) field to do data assimilation in the HR space, to then go back in the LR dimension and only have to run a LR model. (Task 4.4.3)

Code: https://github.com/neccton-algo/Neccton_Super_Resolution/tree/v1.0

Contacts: Antoine Bernigaud (antoine.bernigaud@nersc.no)

Code description: This repo contains the Super Resolution Data Assimilation (SRDA) algorithm for the NECCTON project. It consists in a U-Net model, trained with weights that are downloaded in the notebook Test_ResUnet.ipynb, where the super-resolution can be run. It includes the code used for the training (“training” directory) and to run the full SRDA step (meaning upsampling of the LR fields, assembling of the super-resolved fields into binary files to be read by the model and downsampling back to the LR model) during the assimilation process (“SRDA” directory). The full SRDA algorithm requires an operational model and data assimilation codes and is dependent on them. Therefore, only the super-resolution step can be tried in this repo, and the codes in the training and SRDA directories would need to be adapted to be used in another setup.

3.10 Assimilation of new type of observations in MED (task T4.4.2)

Observational error covariance and model operators to assimilate reflectance measured by satellite

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/diim>

Contacts: Carlos Soto (csoto@ogs.it)

Code description: GPU compatible python code, with a solution of the radiative transfer equation, (RTE) which computes the irradiance at different depths, as well as an estimation of the Remote Sensing Reflectance (RRS), as a function of the density of chlorophyll, detritus and colored dissolved organic matter (CDOM). The code also includes a Bayesian inversion of the RTE, which allows the estimation with uncertainty quantification of the densities of chlorophyll, detritus and CDOM as a function of satellite RRS. From these outputs, an assimilation system can assimilate in an indirect way the satellite RRS, assimilation tested with the Ensemble and Assimilation tool (EAT).

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	D4.3
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2026-06-30	Version	2

3.11 Assimilation of new type of observations in NWS (task T4.4.2)

Observational error covariance and model operators to assimilate reflectance measured by satellite

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/Core-scripts-for-NEMOVAR-Rrs-DA>

Contacts: Jozef Skakala (jos@pml.ac.uk)

Code description: Fortran code, modules for biogeochemistry balancing scheme within the NEMOVAR framework updating (deriving their DA increments) a wide range of optically active tracers from remote sensing reflectance increments. The method is based on 1D test ensemble DA runs based on which we fitted third order polynomial functions describing an inversion model deriving surface tracer concentrations from Rrs at 412nm and Rrs at 650nm wavelengths. This model was subsequently tested in 1D simulations and delivered 12-60% average improvements in Rrs forecasts (depending on the wavelength) relative to the free run, when compared to the satellite data. This is a clear sign that the scheme delivers an overall improvement to bio-optical tracers simulated by ERSEM.

3.12 Assimilation of new type of observations in BLK (task T4.4.2)

Observational error covariance and model operators to assimilate reflectance measured by satellite

Code: <https://github.com/neccton-algo/SORDA>

Contact: Polina Verezemskaya (pverezemskaya@uliege.be)

Code description: SORDA – Spectral Ocean Reflectance Data Assimilation – is an Ensemble Kalman Filter based data assimilation system for multispectral satellite ocean reflectance, which allows for cyclic online assimilation or like in the demonstration kit, offline correction of BGC variables. SORDA uses Ocean Assimilation Kit (OAK) Ensemble Kalman Filter coded in Fortran. Pre- and post-processing is done with Python. Currently, six wavebands of RRS are assimilated into 7 BGC state variables: 3 Black Sea PFTs carbon concentrations, particulate organic carbon concentration, meso- and micro-zooplankton concentrations and gelatinous. Model used for system testing is a 3-D fully coupled NEMO+BAMHBI+RADTRANS setup over the Black Sea, permitting for explicit RRS assessment.

4. Conclusions

Work Package 4 has delivered 12 open-access software tools that address key steps across the operational oceanography value chain—from observations to product generation. These tools support a broad range of functions, including observation handling, model–data integration, model development, and the production of new ecological indicator products.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	D4.3
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Report
Date	2026-06-30	Version	2

Although all codes were developed following the common methodology and best practices described in D4.1 (Brajard et al., 2023), they span multiple programming languages: Fortran (2), Python (7), Julia (1), MATLAB (1), and R (1). This diversity reflects the varying requirements of the tasks involved—for example, handling large datasets and AI libraries, integrating with complex legacy model codes, or processing specialised biological data. It also mirrors the established practices of the different scientific communities contributing to the work.

A key achievement of the work package 4 is the establishment of a shared collaborative environment—the NECCTON-algo GitHub repository—which enhances code sharing, fosters exchange of expertise, and supports discussion across the diverse communities engaged in operational oceanography.

All tools are provided with example use cases and benchmarks to facilitate adoption of the developed methods and to support knowledge transfer among NECCTON partners and stakeholders.

Reference

Brajard J. et al (2023). D4.1 “Description and guideline on the NECCTON-algo GitHub organization”. Deliverable report of project Horizon Europe NECCTON (grant 101081273). DOI 10.5281/zenodo.7867231.

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